

Evaluating 5G-enabled EV Charging Infrastructure’s Resilience Through Stealthy Cyber-Attacks

Dimitrios Psaltis^{*}, Konstantinos Ntouros[†], Alexios Lekidis[‡], Sotirios Brotsis[§], and Nicholas Kolokotronis[¶]

Department of Energy Systems, University of Thessaly, Larissa 41500, Greece

Email: ^{*}dpsaltis@uth.gr, [‡]alekidis@uth.gr

Department of Informatics and Telecommunications, University of the Peloponnese, 22131 Tripolis, Greece

Email: [†]dit20153@go.uop.gr, [§]brotsis@uop.gr, [¶]nkolok@uop.gr

Abstract—The adoption of Electric Vehicles (EVs) over the last years has gained increased attention due to the technological, financial, and environmental gains they offer. However, it has also introduced a vast and exponentially growing threat landscape, which is also complex to analyze. The complexity is even increased when considering the current integration of EV chargers in 5G-oriented network slices and architectures. Hence, the threat landscape analysis becomes crucial to derive the Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (TTPs) that are applicable to the EV-oriented ecosystem as well as their impact on the underlying charging infrastructure. This paper proposes a framework for conducting stealthy attack scenarios and validating their impact on the EV charging infrastructure. In the current version of the framework, two prominent attack types are included: the Denial of Charge when legitimate users are using the EV charging stations and the False Data Injection, tampering with the meter values during and at the end of the charging transaction. For these scenarios, we describe the testbed that is used to conduct the cyber-attacks, provide a detailed overview of the TTPs, and demonstrate their impact on the charging infrastructure.

Index Terms—EV charging, cyber-attacks, OCPP, False Data Injection, Denial of Charge

I. INTRODUCTION

E-mobility is a technological advancement that has been widely adopted over the last years since it provides environmental and financial gains aside from the digitization aspects [1]. The main pillar for the e-mobility ecosystem is the Electric Vehicle (EV) infrastructure with multiple connectivity interfaces to exchange charging data, as well as operational status information, like notifications and diagnostics. With the increase in the acceptance of EVs, the underlying charging infrastructure has evolved as a significant part of smart mobility and energy distribution [2]. As charging systems are significantly relying on internet-connected and cloud-based systems to offer intelligent monitoring, charging, and billing information, but also provide automation and convenience to EV users.

The authors D. Psaltis and K. Ntouros have equally contributed.

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Nevertheless, the increased presence of different interfaces comes with new forms of cyber-attacks that are targeting the EV infrastructure. The risk is even greater when considering that such attacks may propagate even further towards the electricity grid with catastrophic consequences. Examples of such risks include the exposed vulnerabilities for Volkswagen EVs, which resulted in a massive leakage of 800,000 EV drivers’ sensitive data¹. Furthermore, such attacks can also lead to financial impact, as the recent attack against a known EV infrastructure provider², which resulted in withdrawing \$2000 on average from each EV driver using the service.

The attack surface is even expanded since the EV chargers are using cellular connectivity and are gradually integrated in 5G and beyond towards 6G networks [3]. In such networks, there are multiple attack vectors originating from the multi-tenant and multi-domain architectures [4]. To better understand, however, the means that adversaries employ to perform cyber-attacks against the EV infrastructure, as the initial access through, for instance, the cellular infrastructure or the impact that may be caused to the EV infrastructure components, a thorough analysis of the TTPs has to be conducted. To the best of our knowledge, such an analysis is not present up to this point in relevant literature work. Hence, in this paper, we propose a new EV charging framework that is used for the design and implementation of cyber-attack scenarios. Concretely, this paper provides the following contributions:

- Design and implementation of a framework for conducting cyber-attack scenarios against the EV charging infrastructure.
- Development of a testbed for testing prominent EV cyber-attack scenarios, such as Denial of Charge (DoC) and False Data Injection (FDI).

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II provides a background on the EV charging infrastructure as well as the communication and security mechanisms that are used, as well as the related work for cyber-attacks in EV charging scenarios. Then, Section III describes the framework

¹<https://www.darkreading.com/cyber-attacks-data-breaches/volkswagen-breach-exposes-data-of-800k-customers>

²<https://medium.com/@ekarabatsakis/how-customers-helped-us-survive-a-cyber-attack-5ddd2729c3f3>

architecture and testbed implementation for conducting cyber-attack scenarios. The experiments of the conducted attack scenarios on the EV charging infrastructure testbed are described in Section IV. Finally, Section V summarizes the presented work and provides perspectives for future work.

II. BACKGROUND

This section provides an overview of the infrastructure for EV charging and the communication protocols within, along with the related work for EV charging attack scenarios.

A. EV charging infrastructure

The main entities that are involved in EV charging communications are the EVs, the EV Charging Stations (EVCS) and the Charging Station Management System (CSMS), which is a central platform allowing to monitor the status of EVCS and perform diagnostics on their operation; moreover, the CSMS allows the Charge Point Operator (CPO) to have an overview on the EV infrastructure availability as well as configuration and maintenance operations on the EVCSs. In terms of connectivity, the EVCS communicates with the EV through a wired cable, which also delivers the required energy to charge the batteries, while the communication is based on the IEC 61851 standard [5]. Additionally, the communication between the EVCS and the CSMS is based on both wired (i.e., Ethernet) and wireless (i.e., WiFi, cellular networks) interfaces and follows the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) [6]. The usual wireless setup of EVCS is based on 3G SIM cards, and recently are also incorporated in 5G-enabled slices [3].

OCPP is widely used as the communication protocol between the EV charging stations and the Charging Station Management System (CSMS). It includes different versions starting from 1.2, then continued to 1.5, and finally to the OCPP version 1.6 that is currently employed. A new version was also released in January 2025, i.e., version 2.1, allowing bidirectional charging and Vehicle-To-Grid (V2G) scenarios [7]. However, all the existing chargers support version 1.6, which is widely considered a de facto standard for the EV infrastructure. OCPP 1.6 protocol supports several commands for managing the EV charging process and for providing status information. The most important amongst these commands include:

- `StartTransaction` and `StopTransaction` for starting and stopping an EV charging session;
- `MeterValues` for getting real-time current, voltage, and active/reactive power information — which is measured in *watt-hours* (Wh)— consumed while charging; and
- `StatusNotification` for notifying the CPO through the CSMS system of the EVCS current status (i.e., if it is available or charging).

Additionally, an important command for the EVCS operation is `BootNotification`, which allows the CSMS to understand that the EVCS has performed a reboot and is operational. Finally, amongst the most significant OCPP fields is also `meterStop`, since it measures the total energy consumed by

the EV and provides the foundation for calculating the energy consumed and the associated cost on the utility bill. Hence, a data tampering attack on the `meterStop` can result in severe financial losses for the EV users [8].

In terms of security mechanisms, OCPP 1.6 allows for HTTP Basic Authentication as a method of verifying the identity of EVCS during initial connection setup. Before starting a charging session, the legitimacy of a user is inspected through the `Authorize` message, which includes the corresponding Identifier (ID) tag. This tag is compared against the valid ID tags that are stored on the CSMS database. OCPP supports the Transport Layer Security (TLS) protocol, which encrypts communication between the EVCS and the CSMS. Current practices suggest that CPOs shall use TLS 1.2 or higher to provide basic encryption against eavesdropping in the EV charging infrastructure. The security mechanisms of OCPP 1.6 were enriched in OCPP 2.1, and there are also mechanisms for the EV to EVCS communication specified in ISO 15118. However, most CPOs focus on developing the new OCPP 2.1 functionalities rather than investigating its security mechanisms.

B. Related work

The threat landscape in EV infrastructures is an area of growing interest in the literature, since a potential attack may lead to severe consequences both in the EVs as well as the electricity grid [9]. An initial taxonomy and analysis of the threats applicable to EV systems is conducted in [10].

Basnet et al. in [3] performed cyber-attacks against a 5G-oriented EV charging infrastructure, focusing mostly on DoC and FDI scenarios and their infrastructure impact. Nevertheless, these attacks are modeled and simulated in the NetSim simulator³, whereas in our work, we focus on a framework and a testbed for conducting real attack scenarios. Other works are only focused on cyber-attacks targeting the EV charging infrastructure. Jeong et al. [11] presented a data injection attack between the EVCS and the EVs in a simulated environment that resulted in financial losses quantified in electricity cost. Tao et al. [12] conducted a simulated Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack on an EVCS without the incorporation of additional stations or the CSMS. However, with the EV charging points to be substantially escalated in residential and public regions, the research on EVCS security has increased as well [13].

III. FRAMEWORK FOR EV CHARGING CYBER-ATTACKS

The proposed framework provides a testbed of an EV charging ecosystem able to conduct both legitimate and cyber-attack scenarios. The overview of the framework is illustrated in Fig. 1, in which an architectural representation of the EVs, the EVCSs, and the CSMS is presented.

³<https://www.tetcos.com/index.html>

Fig. 1: The high-level architectural diagram of the EV charging infrastructure considered within the proposed framework

A. Legitimate EV charging scenarios

The proposed framework allows for performing legitimate EV charging scenarios in which the charging process is based on the OCPP 1.6 protocol, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The CSMS platform constantly interacts with the EVCSs in a persistent and bidirectional manner via the WebSocket protocol that is used alongside OCPP. A dynamic number of EVCSs, each acting as an OCPP client, can be deployed in the proposed architecture, also linked with a dynamic number of EVs, which can perform charging sessions simultaneously. Currently, an extension for OCPP 2.1 is being developed to support bidirectional charging scenarios and compatible EVCS. The extension includes commands for the `TransactionEvent`, `NotifyEvent` for status notifications, as well as `SetVariables`, and `GetVariables` to set and get the EVCS configurations. Also, `RequestStartTransaction` and `RequestStopTransaction` for starting and stopping the transaction respectively, and setting the charging profile with `SetChargingProfile` will be supported.

Specifically, in the initial step of Fig. 2, the EVCS sends an HTTP request containing the information and its unique ID with which it will be connected in the CSMS database, and upon successful connection, a confirmation message is sent. Then, EVCS sends a message with the `BootNotification` request and the charger information and waits for the accepted response from the CSMS. If there is no active charging session (or a potential EVCS reservation for a charging session via OCPP [14]), the EVCS sends the `StatusNotificationAvailable` message to inform the CSMS that it is available and an EV can be connected for charging. After the EV has been connected to the EVCS, the EV user provides authorization details (i.e., through an `idTag` or in an ad-hoc manner through a credit card payment). In the former case, the `idTag` is verified against an existing CSMS database, and if it is legitimate, the charging process is initiated.

In more detail, the `StartTransaction` message is sent

Fig. 2: The message sequence of a legitimate EV charging scenario in the proposed framework (following OCPP 1.6)

to the CSMS containing the `idTag` and a timestamp with the current time that is used for verification. If the given `idTag` exists and is still active (i.e., has not expired based on the given timestamp), the `StatusNotification` charging message is sent to inform the CSMS that the charging session has been successfully initiated. While charging, the `MeterValues` are periodically received by the CSMS. Finally, when charging is complete, the `StopTransaction` message is sent containing information about the `idTag`, the transaction id, and the `meterStop`.

B. Attack scenarios

As a next step, we present the attacker's involvement within the framework, facilitating the base to explore the common strategies on EV charging cyber-attacks and their implications. In the proposed framework, two main cyber-attack scenarios exist, namely DoC and FDI. These scenarios are considered to be prominent due to their presence in the relevant literature (see Section II), as well as their impact on the EV charging infrastructure. Specifically, the impact of both cyber-attacks is linked to the financial losses on both the EV user and the CPO, who is responsible for supplying the energy. Furthermore, in

Fig. 3: The DoC attack steps during the charging session

the FDI attack, the impact can be more severe, resulting in regulatory issues and reputational impact for the CPO, who needs to ensure continuous compliance with the Measuring Instruments Directive (Directive 2014/32/EU)⁴ in many EU countries. In addition, the tampered electricity values may also cause an electricity grid stress.

Algorithm 1 Detection of EVCS and CSMS

- 1: **Require:** Kali Linux system
- 2: Connect to the same network with EVCS and CSMS
- 3: Run Bettercap
- 4: Set `arp.spoof.full duplex to true`
 - ▷ Attack all targets and gateway
- 5: Set `arp.spoof on`
 - ▷ Enable ARP spoofing
- 6: Set `net.sniff.verbose to true`
 - ▷ Display all captured packets
- 7: Set `net.sniff.output <filename>.pcap`
 - ▷ Save captured packets to file
- 8: Set `net.sniff on`
 - ▷ Enable packet sniffing
- 9: Open the `.pcap` file in Wireshark
- 10: Detect the network IPs sending WebSocket packets
- 11: **Output:** IP addresses of EVCS and CSMS

Initially, for performing the attack scenarios, the steps of Alg. 1 are followed. Specifically, the attacker gains access to the local network, where the CSMS and EVCSs are located. By identifying the IPs of the CSMS and EVCSs, the attacker launches a MitM attack using ARP spoofing. As presented in Fig. 3, after the MitM attack, all the communication messages are traversing through the attacker. Therefore, to launch a DoC or an FDI attack, the appropriate message needs to be falsified. Each message in the OCPP protocol has two parts, the *Request* and the *Confirmation*, starting with the numbers 2 and 3 as

Fig. 4: The FDI attack sequence during the charging session

well as with the following formats “2, UUID, Message” and “3, UUID, message”, respectively.

The DoC is initiated based on the steps of Alg. 1. In particular, the attack is launched when a `StartTransaction` request is sent from the EVCS to CSMS, which would normally lead to the message’s acceptance or rejection. Instead, the attacker transforms this request into another OCPP message for performing a Hard Reset. Specifically, the ‘3,UUID, `StartTransaction.conf`’ message is transformed by the attack to the “2, `new_uuid`, `Reset.req`”. Therefore, the EVCS receives a message to perform a reset instead of starting the charging session, and as a result, reboots. On the other hand, the EV driver is attempting to charge, without being aware of the attack, and as soon as the charger is back online, attempts to start the charging session again with the same outcome. Since the attack is launched on all the available chargers in the network, the same result, i.e., a DoC attack, occurs if the driver attempts to charge the EV at any EVCS in the same network.

Similarly to the DoC attack, in FDI, the attacker falsifies the appropriate messages exchanged between the CSMS and the EVCSs, where the steps for performing the FDI attack are illustrated in Fig. 4. More specifically, the attacker spoofs the `MeterValue.req` message sent by the EVCS to the CSMS by maliciously modifying the value of the energy consumed that is measured in Wh. While the active charging session is being finalized through the `StopTransaction.req`, the attacker falsifies the charging values of the total energy consumed by the EV that is present in the `meterStop` value. Thus, the uniformity of the total consumed energy with the intermediate `MeterValues` makes the attack more difficult to detect. The detailed steps of the FDI attack are explained in Alg. 2, which is discussed in detail in Section IV.

⁴<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32014L0032>

Fig. 5: The experimental testbed that was used for carrying out the cyber-attacks against the EV charging infrastructure

IV. EXPERIMENTS

This section aims to evaluate the adversarial interference on the proposed framework with a DoC attack and a manipulation of the reported meter values within the scope of an FDI attack. In both attacks, the communication between the EV charger and the CSMS is intercepted to modify the OCPP messages, where different messages are modified in each attack.

A. EV charging testbed

The testbed architecture is presented in Fig. 5 and is built on top of SAP's e-Mobility charging stations simulator⁵, which simulates the behavior of the EVCSs and the charging EVs. The CSMS in the architecture is based on the Steve project⁶, a smart charging system for EVs that is responsible for the collection of real-time data from distributed charging stations. These data are linked to energy consumption, session metrics, users' activities, and stations' status, thus enabling CPOs to monitor systems' performance and respond to possible issues promptly.

The Steve CSMS also allows the authentication of users' sessions, which is performed via secure identifiers as Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) cards (or simply ID tags), but also the secure preservation of logs about each user's interactions and session data. Steve's adoption in the proposed framework offers additional services for remote management, allowing CPOs to initiate or terminate charging transactions, reset hardware, and conduct firmware updates. Such functionalities not only depict valuable insights for billing, but also provide information about the system's analytics and optimization, as well as efficient maintenance and diagnostics for CPOs [15].

B. Cyber-attack scenario implementation

The conducted experiments were based on three KEBA AC and one ABB DC charging stations, that is, four EV charging

stations in total. Nevertheless, the proposed framework is built having scalability in mind, and therefore, the experiments can be conducted in a more extensive environment. The attacks are launched using Kali Linux⁷ Operating System (OS), along with the mitmproxy tool⁸ for conducting the MiTM attack and the Bettercap tool⁹ for network layer monitoring.

Initially, the attacker connects to the same local area network as the EVCS and CSMS systems, detects the IP addresses to spoof, and initiates the cyber-attack (Alg. 1). With the command set `arp.spoof.full duplex`, the attacker performs ARP spoofing on both targeted systems and the gateway to monitor network activity. Then, using `net.sniff.verbose` and `net.sniff.output` records each packet sent to identify the WebSocket packets, while all the traffic is saved in a Packet Capture (i.e., `.pcap`) file. Finally, the Wireshark protocol analysis tool¹⁰ allows to detect which IP addresses exchange WebSocket packets. Depending on the WebSocket message that is transmitted in the network, the attacker detects the IP address of the CSMS and those of the EVCSs (from Alg. 1). Then, using mitmproxy as a transparent proxy, the traffic is redirected to a proxy server at the network layer, requiring no configuration at the (targeted) client side.

Algorithm 2 Falsification of meter values

- 1: **Require:** Algorithm 1
 - 2: Run mitmproxy as a transparent proxy
 - 3: ARP spoofing between EVCSs, CSMS
 - 4: **if** packet contains WebSocket messages **then**
 - 5: Get last message \rightarrow latest_msg
 - \triangleright Decode as UTF-8
 - 6: **if** identify MeterValues and Wh **then**
 - 7: Value of unit Wh \leftarrow Reduce value by 50%
 - 8: Modified value \leftarrow Value of unit Wh
 - 9: **else if** identify StopTransaction and
 - 10: meterStop **then**
 - 11: meterStop \leftarrow Reduce value by 50%
 - 12: Modified meterStop \leftarrow meterStop
 - 13: **end**
 - 14: **end**
 - 15: Convert msg to JSON string \rightarrow updated_msg
 - \triangleright Encode as UTF-8
 - 16: **Output:** Modified energy consumption data
-

At the same time, the attacker performs an ARP spoofing attack between the EVCSs and the CSMS (as mentioned in Alg. 1) and configures the way to launch the data falsification attack (steps 4-15 of Alg. 2). Therefore, when a WebSocket packet containing an OCPP message is detected, mitmproxy decodes it as UTF-8 and if the keywords MeterValues and Wh are identified, modifies the Wh by reducing it by a

⁷<https://www.kali.org/>

⁸<https://mitmproxy.org/>

⁹<https://www.bettercap.org/>

¹⁰<https://www.wireshark.org/>

⁵<https://github.com/sap/e-mobility-charging-stations-simulator>

⁶<https://github.com/steve-community/steve>

Fig. 6: Original and falsified meter values of the FDI attack that targets the charging session

custom value, which for this experiment is set to 50%. Then, the modified message is encoded into a UTF-8 JSON string and is sent back to the CSMS. The same happens when the keywords `StopTransaction` and `meterStop` are also detected. The mitmproxy modifies the value of `MeterStop` by reducing it by 50% and then encodes it back to UTF-8 JSON string and sends it to CSMS. Therefore, by falsifying the intermediate `MeterValues` and the final `Stopvalue` by the same percentage, the attack detection becomes challenging.

The result of this attack is presented in Fig. 6. As depicted in the figure, the energy consumption during the charging session reaches almost 2.4 kWh, while the consumption received by the CSMS is reduced to half of the original value, i.e., 1.2 kWh, as a consequence of the FDI attack. In particular, Fig. 7 presents the logs from the mitmproxy environment where the cyber-attack is performed. The messages containing the original meter values are marked with a green bounding box, whereas the modified messages received by the CSMS are marked with a red one.

```

user@kali: ~
File Actions Edit View Help
Events
Info: [19:57:36.311] Original MeterValues Message: b[2, "feefee5f-d613-451f-b8b1-929c9757bef3", "MeterValues", {"connectorId": 1, "transactionId": 206, "meterValue": [{"timestamp": "2025-05-09T16:57:36.323Z", "sampledValue": [{"unit": "V", "measurand": "Voltage", "value": "225.25"}, {"unit": "V", "measurand": "Voltage", "value": "225.25", "phase": "L1-N"}, {"unit": "V", "measurand": "Voltage", "value": "225.25", "phase": "L2-N"}, {"unit": "V", "measurand": "Voltage", "value": "225.25", "phase": "L3-N"}, {"unit": "W", "measurand": "Power.Active.Import", "value": "7064.22"}, {"unit": "W", "measurand": "Power.Active.Import", "value": "3262.54", "phase": "L1-N"}, {"unit": "W", "measurand": "Power.Active.Import", "value": "3618", "phase": "L2-N"}, {"unit": "W", "measurand": "Power.Active.Import", "value": "183.68", "phase": "L3-N"}, {"unit": "A", "measurand": "Current.Import", "value": "9.55"}, {"unit": "A", "measurand": "Current.Import", "value": "12.3", "phase": "L1"}, {"unit": "A", "measurand": "Current.Import", "value": "11.32", "phase": "L2"}, {"unit": "A", "measurand": "Current.Import", "value": "5.04", "phase": "L3"}, {"unit": "Wh", "value": "2379.7"}]}]]]
Info: [19:57:36.311] Modified Wh Value: 1189.85
Info: [19:57:36.311] Modified MeterValues Message: b[2, "feefee5f-d613-451f-b8b1-929c9757bef3", "MeterValues", {"connectorId": 1, "transactionId": 206, "meterValue": [{"timestamp": "2025-05-09T16:57:36.323Z", "sampledValue": [{"unit": "V", "measurand": "Voltage", "value": "225.25"}, {"unit": "V", "measurand": "Voltage", "value": "225.25", "phase": "L1-N"}, {"unit": "V", "measurand": "Voltage", "value": "225.25", "phase": "L2-N"}, {"unit": "V", "measurand": "Voltage", "value": "225.25", "phase": "L3-N"}, {"unit": "W", "measurand": "Power.Active.Import", "value": "7064.22"}, {"unit": "W", "measurand": "Power.Active.Import", "value": "3262.54", "phase": "L1-N"}, {"unit": "W", "measurand": "Power.Active.Import", "value": "3618", "phase": "L2-N"}, {"unit": "W", "measurand": "Power.Active.Import", "value": "183.68", "phase": "L3-N"}, {"unit": "A", "measurand": "Current.Import", "value": "9.55"}, {"unit": "A", "measurand": "Current.Import", "value": "12.3", "phase": "L1"}, {"unit": "A", "measurand": "Current.Import", "value": "11.32", "phase": "L2"}, {"unit": "A", "measurand": "Current.Import", "value": "5.04", "phase": "L3"}, {"unit": "Wh", "value": "1189.85"}]}]]]
Info: [19:57:56.189] Original StopTransaction Message: b[2, "eda7c2c0-a578-4d47-ab1a-ce231af34ce9", "StopTransaction", {"idTag": "Dimitris", "meterStop": 2380, "timestamp": "2025-05-09T16:57:56.201Z", "transactionId": 206}]
Info: [19:57:56.190] Modified StopTransaction Message: b[2, "eda7c2c0-a578-4d47-ab1a-ce231af34ce9", "StopTransaction", {"idTag": "Dimitris", "meterStop": 1190, "timestamp": "2025-05-09T16:57:56.201Z", "transactionId": 206}]
[19:57:56.190] [transparent] [scripts:1] [192.168.201.138:8080]
Events: Scroll down Scroll up Clear
Proxy: Help Back Events Options Intercept Filter Save flows

```

Fig. 7: Log fragment from mitmproxy tool during the FDI attack with parts of an exchanged OCPP 1.6 message

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a newly introduced framework for conducting EV charging attack scenarios in a 5G-enabled infrastructure, to aid in understanding the attackers' TTPs and their impact on the EV infrastructure. Future work aims at extending the attack scenarios considered as part of the framework. To this end, prominent attack scenarios that also relate to manipulating legitimate RFID tags and their associated timestamps to invalidate them and prevent a charging session from starting will be considered. Moreover, the charging profile manipulation and the parameters that should be used to stress the energy grid are also planned to be demonstrated. Finally, we will also consider introducing malware to cause DDoS attacks against multiple EVCSs located at different network segments, and we will investigate their impact on the EV charging service along with the cascading effects on the electricity grid.

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